

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This fifth regular issue of J.UCS once more contains a wide range of papers: three are more theoretical in nature, one is a nice contribution to hypermedia aspects, and the last is a paper dealing with general and legal problems threatening the spread of Internet. I hope more than one paper will attract your attention.

Note: if you have remarks concerning any of the papers you are welcome to send them to jucs@iicm.tu-graz.ac.at with a note whether I can use parts of them for publication in J.UCS: if so, your remarks will be added as "annotations" to the papers at issue, a feature where an electronic journal really can "shine" in comparison with a printed one: this feature is available in J.UCS yet we have not used it, sofar.

There is one other point worth noting: in all issues to date we have presented all papers in hypertext format and in PostScript. However, since simple hypertext mark-up languages like HTML 2.0 or HTF do not support formulae all formulae have been treated as inline images. In theoretical papers this has lead to the ridiculous situation that some papers contained thousands of tiny inline images! We propose to not use such format for very formula oriented papers in the future until HTML 3.0 will be fully standardized and capable of handling formulae in a reasonable fashion. If you are strongly opposed to our decision we would like to hear about it, and why!

Yours cordially

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer, Managing Editor
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PS: Have your heard about the new **Web Society**? If not, have a look at <http://info.websoc.at> and join the society, if you feel you can support its main ideas. Thank you!